

SUPPLEMENT 1

Detailed study descriptions of case reports, retrospective cohort studies and prospective studies on teriparatide use and AFF.

IA. Case reports: incomplete AFF and use of teriparatide

In 13 patients with incomplete AFFs the course of radiological healing was described after or during teriparatide use.

Radiological healing within one year of teriparatide use was reported of nine patients with 11 incomplete AFFs. These included four patients with five incomplete AFFs who underwent prophylactic surgery (1-3) and five patients with six incomplete AFFs that were treated conservatively with teriparatide only (4-8).

The surgically treated cases comprised three patients who started immediately after the prophylactic surgery (1, 2) and one patient who started teriparatide five months postoperatively because of delayed healing of a contralateral complete AFF (3). The latter case by Fukuda et al. showed complete union of both AFFs after three months of teriparatide use. Tsuchie et al. reported two patients who were pain-free within two to three weeks following the surgery and a fracture line that was almost invisible within three to six months postoperatively in three incomplete AFFs (1). Chew et al. described a case with good callus formation in a patient who was pain-free two months postoperatively (2).

In three of six incomplete AFFs treated conservatively a fracture line was visible. In one case, the lucent line had completely disappeared within six months (5). In two cases, the fracture line and pain diminished after starting teriparatide, but the lucent line was only completely closed after 12 months of teriparatide use (7, 8). This included a case of a 63-year-old man with osteogenesis imperfecta who refused any medical or surgical treatment during two years before commencing teriparatide (8).

The remaining three incomplete AFFs without a fracture line concerned one patient with bilateral focal thickening that had almost completely flattened after 18 months of teriparatide (although the incomplete AFFs recurred on bone scan and X-rays after denosumab 1.5 years later) (4), whilst in another patient focal cortical thickening was reduced according to the authors (6) from 12.2mm to 11.3mm after two years of teriparatide. However, it is unclear in both cases whether this flattening is a significant decrease, or if this could also be explained by variation in positioning and measurement on the X-ray, or if it could simply reflect the natural healing of incomplete AFF over time rather than a healing effect of teriparatide itself.

One patient with bilateral incomplete AFFs with radiolucent lines was electively operated because of persistent hotspots on bone scintigraphy and a waddling gait despite six months of teriparatide treatment (9). After one year callus formation was visible on X-rays. In this 67-year-old Armenian woman genetic testing revealed hypophosphatasia, after she had been treated with alendronate for 10 years.

Persistent non-union after more than one year was found in two patients with conservatively managed AFFs and a visible fracture line (10, 11). One case reported that it took 15 months before the fracture line completely disappeared even though teriparatide was started one month after the diagnosis, but it is noteworthy that the pain did improve within the first months of teriparatide and the patient was able to walk after 10 months (10). In another case of bilateral incomplete AFFs, full healing was seen only 22 months after the diagnosis on MRI scan despite the use of teriparatide 20ug daily during the past 19 months (11).

Progression to complete AFF was reported in one patient with bilateral incomplete AFFs with radiolucent lines whilst on teriparatide for two months and the subsequent fracture healing of the operated femur was delayed up to 18 months (12).

IB. Case reports: complete AFF and teriparatide use

In 17 patients with 20 complete AFFs the radiological healing was reported after or during the use of teriparatide.

Fifteen patients with 18 complete AFFs reached fracture healing within one year of teriparatide. In 13 patients with 15 complete AFFs full fracture union was achieved within six months (3, 5, 13-23), and full consolidation was reported after one year in two patients with three complete AFFs (24, 25). Duration of teriparatide use varied from two months (16) up to two years, whilst in other cases the duration was not specified. In nine patients teriparatide was started within two months after the first surgery, whilst six patients were prescribed teriparatide because of slow fracture healing (3, 17-20), starting 12 months postoperatively at the latest. This includes one case (17) in which bisphosphonate treatment was continued during the first year after the occurrence of AFF before switching to teriparatide. There was one report of teriparatide use in a patient with metastatic bone disease (21). The first complete AFF was presumed to be pathological fracture and bisphosphonates were continued until she sustained a contralateral complete AFF two year later, after which teriparatide was then started with successful healing within five months and a bone biopsy from the fracture site did not show malignancy (21).

Three patients with unilateral AFF did not achieve fracture healing whilst on teriparatide (12, 26, 27). One patient had non-union regardless of 24 months teriparatide. Consolidation did occur after replacement of the intramedullary nail and switching to strontium ranelate (26). The second case was prescribed teriparatide seven months postoperatively because of delayed healing, but still had non-union after a full treatment course of 24 months (27). The AFF only healed after re-operation to replace the plate and sliding screw with an intramedullary gamma-nail. The third case concerned an incomplete AFF that had progressed to a complete fracture

whilst using teriparatide for two months and postoperatively the healing process was delayed up to 18 months (12).

Three other patients with unilateral AFF were reported with signs of abnormal fracture healing; however, follow-up was limited to four or five months of teriparatide and thus the status of fracture healing at six months could not be determined (24, 28, 29). These included a patient who had insufficient callus bridging six months after the diagnosis following five months of teriparatide (28). A second patient with a history of osteonecrosis of the jaw, started using teriparatide eight months postoperatively because of delayed healing of AFF, without any effect after five months of teriparatide (29). In the third patient, no effect was seen of four months teriparatide which was initiated 18 months postoperatively due to delayed healing (24).

IC. Case reports: occurrence of new AFF during or after teriparatide

Four patients have been newly diagnosed with five AFFs after teriparatide use (22, 23, 30, 31).

One patient with a complete AFF who initially had a normal femoral cortex of the contralateral femur on X-ray, was newly diagnosed with a contralateral incomplete AFF after 18 months of postoperative teriparatide treatment and four months of strontium ranelate (22). In the second case, a contralateral incomplete AFF was diagnosed 22 months after the first complete AFF and during the eleventh month of teriparatide use, which was prescribed due to high fracture risk (23). Thirdly, a patient was reported with a newly diagnosed incomplete AFF that required immediate surgery whilst on teriparatide treatment since four months, which was initiated because of a non-healing metatarsal fracture (30). This patient had been treated with bisphosphonates for over a decade and (short-term) teriparatide use did not seem to prevent a pending complete fracture in this case.

The fourth case was a first presentation of simultaneous complete AFF and contralateral incomplete AFF two years after discontinuation of teriparatide without any antiresorptive use in the meantime; although this patient had prior exposure to antiresorptives for eight years in the past (31). This indicates that even anabolic drug agents and a drug holiday of several years from bisphosphonates does not protect from developing a new AFF.

II. Retrospective cohort studies on AFF and use of teriparatide

Nine retrospective cohorts described use of teriparatide in patients with AFF. Five cohorts involved incomplete AFFs only (32-36), three cohorts described complete AFFs only (37-39) and one cohort included both incomplete and complete AFFs (40).

Lee et al. (2013) published a retrospective cohort of 51 patients with 65 incomplete AFFs from four hospitals in South Korea with a minimum follow-up period of 12 months (32). After the diagnosis, limited weight-bearing was advised, but surgery was performed in those with intractable pain or when complete fracture occurred. In 26 patients with 31 incomplete AFFs (47.6%), surgery was required at the mean of 9.4 months (range 1-26 months). Surgery was required in 17 AFFs for intractable pain and in 14 AFFs for completion of the fracture. Teriparatide was used by 19 patients with 22 incomplete AFFs for a mean of 4.6 months, ranging from one to 10 months. Teriparatide was given in seven patients that required surgery and in 12 patients that did not undergo surgery. Use of teriparatide did not significantly reduce the need for surgery ($p = 0.210$), although the subtrochanteric fracture location was associated with requirement for fixation rather than diaphyseal localization ($p=0.018$). This study does not report on duration of fracture healing and could therefore not be included in the pooled data shown in **Table 4**. The number of patients on teriparatide with elective surgery and those with surgery after completion of AFF and the presence of radiolucent lines in incomplete AFFs are not mentioned in the article.

Saleh et al. reported 10 women with 14 incomplete AFFs (33).

Five AFFs in four patients did not show a fracture line but did have periosteal and bone marrow edema visible on MRI scan; these AFFs were conservatively treated with partial weight bearing and teriparatide for two years. None had progression to a complete AFF and all patients reported improvement in pain and function. The focal cortical thickening on the X-ray remained unchanged, but the MRI scans showed complete resolution of edema after three months in all five cases.

Nine AFFs in the remaining six patients showed a radiolucent line. These patients were given a trial of teriparatide for three months, except for one AFF that was treated with miacalcin (salmon calcitonin) instead because this patient had received radiation on the skeleton in the past. Two AFFs in two patients had healed radiographically and clinically within three months of teriparatide use, but preventive surgery was performed in the remaining seven AFFs because of persistent pain and a radiolucent line at three-month follow-up. For the summary in **Table 4**, it was extracted from this paper that seven non-operated incomplete AFFs in six patients healed within six months on teriparatide treatment.

Petraszko et al. presented a retrospective imaging study comparing tomosynthesis and X-ray to detect fracture lines in eight patients with localized cortical thickening of 10 femora (34). A fracture line was visible using one or both techniques in all patients except for one 61-year-old-man who turned out to have sustained a trauma of the upper leg and had never used bisphosphonates. The authors stated that the focal cortical thickening was due to a chronic ossification of a subperiosteal hematoma in this case. The remaining seven patients were all women on prolonged bisphosphonate use over seven years, of whom six started on teriparatide and one underwent prophylactic surgery without teriparatide administration.

Three women had prodromal thigh pain. During a follow-up period of three to almost five years, none of the patients treated conservatively had completion of the fracture. The fracture line disappeared in two patients with teriparatide after six and 12 months.

Sato et al. reported 12 Japanese women with focal thickening of 20 femora without visible fracture lines (35). Incomplete AFF was defined as development of a fracture line penetrating from the tip of the localized bone reaction on X-ray, without displacement of the femur. The authors retrospectively compared the shape of the focal cortical thickening in a group of seven patients that immediately discontinued bisphosphonates after the diagnosis to five patients who continued on bisphosphonate therapy for two years. All five patients on continued use of bisphosphonates deteriorated: one had a complete AFF after 18 months, one patient developed a visible fracture line, two patients had de novo contralateral beaking and one had increased height of the focal cortical thickening. When bisphosphonates were discontinued two years later, two of five patients were prescribed teriparatide treatment, whilst in seven patients who discontinued immediately, four were switched to teriparatide treatment. Of these six patients on teriparatide, one patient who was discontinued on bisphosphonates immediately after focal cortical thickening was established, had progression to a complete AFF following eight months of teriparatide. In all other teriparatide users the focal cortical thickening improved or remained unchanged. The decision to use teriparatide depended on the attending physician. For the pooled data in **Table 4**, only progression to complete AFF in one patient on teriparatide could be established, whilst for the other incomplete AFFs the fracture healing was not specified.

In a conference abstract by Cheung et al. a cohort was reported of 22 postmenopausal women with 27 incomplete AFFs treated with teriparatide (36). Four patients underwent prophylactic

surgery. Of the remaining 19 patients on conservative management, follow-up imaging was available for 15 patients with 19 incomplete AFFs. Every six months for up to two years, the depth of the fracture line through the cortex was measured on conventional radiographs and CT scans during teriparatide therapy. Of these fractures, two healed during teriparatide, five were consolidating, 12 remained unchanged and none had progressed to a complete fracture at last follow-up. However, four patients developed new fracture lines in the same femur of the original incomplete AFF despite teriparatide treatment. It is not stated at what time-points the healing occurred and this cohort is therefore not included in the summary of data in **Table 4**.

Miyakoshi et al. reported a cohort of 45 AFFs in 34 Japanese women (40). Teriparatide was given in 11 complete AFFs and 10 incomplete AFFs, whilst 21 complete AFFs and 3 incomplete AFFs were not treated with teriparatide. Eight incomplete AFFs (18%) did not require surgery; in all other AFFs surgical intervention was performed. All patients were followed up for an interval of one to three months until fracture union was observed. Fracture union following incomplete AFFs was defined as the disappearance of the fracture line. Normal union was defined as fracture healing within six months. Delayed union was defined as fracture healing after more than six months but within two years. Non-union was defined as a fracture that did not achieve union or showed pseudo-joint during final follow-up visit or after more than two years.

In the teriparatide group, 11 complete AFFs (100%) and eight incomplete AFFs (80%) of whom half underwent surgery, healed within six months; two incomplete AFFs showed delayed healing including one case with surgical management. In the non-teriparatide group considering the complete AFFs only, 12 healed within six months, eight showed delayed healing and one case had nonunion. Regarding the incomplete AFFs in the non-teriparatide group, two achieved union within six months and one had delayed fracture healing, all on

conservative management. Taking into account surgically managed AFFs only (21 in the non-teriparatide versus 11 in the teriparatide group), time to fracture healing was significantly shorter in the teriparatide-treated group (5.4 months vs. 8.6 months; $p=0.012$) and the frequency of delayed healing or non-union was significantly lower in teriparatide-treated group ($p = 0.014$). Sub-analysis for the conservatively treated AFFs showed no significant differences between groups, but these compromised only three AFFs in the non-teriparatide group and five in the teriparatide-group. We categorized ten AFFs ($n=8$ complete AFF without teriparatide, $n=1$ non-operated incomplete AFF with teriparatide and $n=1$ surgically treated incomplete AFF with teriparatide) that healed between six to 24 months as “healed at 12 months” in **Table 4**.

Takakubo et al. reported 11 AFFs in eight women with rheumatic disease who all underwent surgical procedures and had a postoperative follow-up of at least one year (37). The authors do not specify whether these AFFs were complete or incomplete. For the combined data in **Table 4**, these AFFs were categorized as complete AFFs.

Five AFFs were treated with a combination of teriparatide and low-intensity pulsed ultrasonography (LIPUS), three AFFs with LIPUS only, and three contralateral AFFs without administration of teriparatide or LIPUS. The mean duration of healing of five AFFs on teriparatide was 11.5 months and 13.3 months in the six AFFs without teriparatide. Of the teriparatide-treated group, one AFF healed at six months, two at one year, one at 16 months, and one did not achieve fracture healing at one year but was then lost to follow-up. In the LIPUS-only group, fracture healing of three AFFs was achieved at 12, 13 and 24 months, respectively (mean 16.3 months). In the AFF without teriparatide and without LIPUS, healing was achieved at nine, 10 and 12 months, respectively (10.3 months).

In four AFFs, bisphosphonates were not immediately discontinued after the occurrence of AFF, one in the teriparatide-treated group, one in the LIPUS group, and two of those with no additional therapy after the surgery. These four AFFs did heal within 10 to 13 months.

Yeh et al. retrospectively reviewed 13 Taiwanese women with 16 complete AFFs of which eight were treated with teriparatide for at least six months (39). They all underwent internal fixation with intramedullary osteosynthesis. One patient had initially refused teriparatide but did start treatment soon after a contralateral AFF and delayed union of the first AFF. Six teriparatide-treated AFFs were completely healed at six months follow-up, versus four non-teriparatide treated AFFs. The remaining AFFs concerned five AFFs with slower fracture healing but good consolidation at nine months' follow-up and one case of implant failure in the non-teriparatide group, a 61-year-old female who needed two revision surgeries thereafter. The average time to union was 4.4 months in the teriparatide-treated group versus 6.2 months in the non-teriparatide group ($p=0.116$). The authors reported a significantly better functional outcome and lower pain scores at six months postoperatively in the teriparatide-group, but at three and 12 months there were no significant differences between groups.

Lee et al. (2017) described a cohort from seven hospitals in South Korea of 44 women with 46 complete AFFs with a minimum follow-up period of six months or until fracture union was achieved (38). All patients underwent intramedullary nailing. Fracture union was defined as callus bridging of three or four cortices. When no radiographic evidence of union was seen within six months, this was labeled as delayed healing. Fixation failure was defined as absence of complete bony union one year following surgery or implant failure during the follow-up period. Three groups were distinguished: 20 patients who discontinued on bisphosphonates (21 AFFs), 10 patients who continued bisphosphonates (11 AFFs) and 14

patients who started teriparatide (14 AFFs). In the teriparatide-treated group 11 AFFs healed within six months (78.5%), compared to 13 in the discontinued group (61.9%), and 5 (45.5%) in the group that continued on bisphosphonates. Eventually, in 44 of 46 AFFs complete bony union was achieved without further surgical intervention within one year. Two AFFs needed revision surgery due to non-healing, but it is not stated whether these patients had discontinued bisphosphonates or had used teriparatide. There were no significant differences in time to union among these three groups ($p=0.08$), although a more favorable trend was seen in the teriparatide group (19.7 weeks), compared to the groups that discontinued bisphosphonates (26.5 weeks) and those on continued use of bisphosphonates (28.4 weeks).

III. Prospective studies on AFF and use of teriparatide

Chiang et al. published a prospective study in 13 women and one man with a median age of 76 years, including six cases of complete AFF and eight cases of incomplete AFF (41). Incomplete AFF was diagnosed when a fracture line was visible or abnormalities on MRI or technetium scans were suggestive of a stress fracture in the lateral cortex. Five patients started on teriparatide 20ug daily for six months, including four patients with incomplete AFFs with ongoing pain and a persistent fracture line since eight to 12 months after the diagnosis and one patient following completion of the AFF. The remaining nine patients (five with incomplete AFFs and four with complete AFFs) were not prescribed teriparatide due to medical contra-indications or refusal to self-inject.

In the teriparatide-treated group, two patients had complete healing and three had partial healing. Two patients were pain-free and three had improved pain scores. In the non-teriparatide group, three patients needed prophylactic surgery of whom one sustained a contralateral AFF, one had fracture union and was pain-free one year postoperatively and a third had poor healing and ongoing pain. The remaining four patients with complete AFFs

and two patients with incomplete AFFs without teriparatide all had non-union and persistent pain one year post-fracture. Based on the available data it was not possible to distinguish the outcome in between complete AFF and incomplete AFF cases separately, and the follow-up time is not explicitly stated in this article; therefore, this article is not included in **Table 4**.

This anecdotal evidence suggests a favorable effect of teriparatide in four incomplete AFFs and one complete AFF, but the healing duration for incomplete AFF and complete AFFs separately are not explicitly stated in this article.

Greenspan et al. published a randomized pilot trial in 13 patients comparing teriparatide immediately after surgical intervention (n=7) versus delayed teriparatide six months following the surgery (n=6) (42). All patients were female with a median age of 74 years. All but one patient had sustained a complete AFF and four individuals had periprosthetic fractures. Conventional X-rays were done at baseline and six and 12 months after the acute fracture. Additionally, the subjects on delayed teriparatide had an X-ray at 18 months. The fracture healing was assessed on continuity of the bone, disappearance of lucencies, callus formation, and alignment of proximal and distal fracture fragments. These four parameters were combined in a composite score with a maximum of 16 points, a higher score indicating better bone healing. At six and 12 months, no statistically significant differences were found in composite scores between the immediate and delayed group (12.6 vs 11.2, $p = 0.3820$; 15.4 vs 13.2, $p = 0.1456$), with a more favorable trend in the immediate group towards fracture healing. It is not stated in this article how many AFFs or patients had achieved full bone union at six or 12 months of teriparatide; therefore, it is not eligible for the pooled data in **Table 4**. The authors do report that one implant failure occurred in the delayed group after 12 months of teriparatide and that there were no cases of non-union in either of the two groups at any time point. No occurrence of contralateral AFF was mentioned. The authors concluded that immediate start of teriparatide appeared to result in improved healing.

Watts et al. prospectively followed 14 women with a median age of 68 years, starting with teriparatide after complete AFF or incomplete AFF (43). The commencement of teriparatide varied from 52 days to 410 days after the AFF. There was radiographic follow-up of the fracture status at month 12 and month 24, but not at six months which made the assessment of healing time of AFFs not suitable for the pooling of the data in **Table 4** apart from two cases of progression from incomplete to complete AFFs. The study population was comprised of 10 complete AFFs in nine patients and seven incomplete AFFs in five patients. Four patients with incomplete AFFs were managed conservatively, whilst one patient had surgical intervention prior to starting teriparatide. Four complete AFFs showed full fracture union after one year in three patients, one had nonunion and the other five had partial healing after one year of teriparatide. Four incomplete AFFs had partially healed including the surgically treated incomplete AFF and the other three incomplete AFFs remained unchanged after one year of teriparatide. Two patients with complete AFF sustained a complete contralateral AFF whilst on teriparatide, after nine days and 21 months, respectively. Focal thickening was visible of the involved femur prior to starting teriparatide in both of these patients. To establish the effect of teriparatide, it is important to know about the fracture healing status prior to using teriparatide. However, the authors do not state if complete AFFs had malunion before starting teriparatide that could explain why seven patients started anabolic therapy more than four months after the diagnosis. Also, it is not reported how many incomplete AFFs had radiolucent lines and how partial healing was defined in cases without visible fracture lines. Another limitation is the lack of a control group.

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